

PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS OF HYPERANDROGENISM SYNDROME

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Hyperandrogenemia is a common endocrine disorder. Hyperandrogenism syndrome refers to conditions associated with excessive production of androgen hormones in women. These conditions lead to metabolic pathology, hirsutism, menstrual cycle disorders, miscarriage, and infertility.

Research objective. To identify problems in the diagnosis of hyperandrogenism syndrome through an analysis of modern literature.

Materials and methods. A search was conducted in the literature and open databases among publications over the past 5 years. More than one hundred thousand publications on the problem were identified, and the most relevant ones were selected from among them.

Results. Hyperandrogenism is divided into three types: idiopathic, receptor, transport, and iatrogenic. Idiopathic hyperandrogenism is characterized by an increase in the amount of androgens detected by laboratory tests. The receptor form is accompanied by an increase in the number and sensitivity of androgen “target” receptors. In the transport form, there is a violation of the function of blood proteins that bind testosterone. The iatrogenic form is associated with the intake of drugs with androgenic properties. The American and European reproductive medicine societies have recommended the use of clinical, laboratory and ultrasound examinations in the diagnosis of hyperandrogenism syndrome. However, the principles inherent in the forms of hyperandrogenism and their various clinical manifestations are still not fully described in the literature.

Conclusion. Biochemical confirmation of hyperandrogenemia is not the final, but the initial stage of the examination, therefore, a differential diagnostic approach is required to search for its causes. Despite the wide possibilities of methods for diagnosing hyperandrogenism syndrome, the development of early diagnostic principles specific to its forms and various clinical manifestations is one of the important problems for gynecological practice.